

Integration of Mathematical Modelling in Engineering Education: A Qualitative Study on Differential Equations

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Abstract

This study conducts a qualitative assessment of mathematical modeling in engineering education via a differential equations course at the Universidad Nacional de Colombia, Palmira Campus. By focusing on individual environmental engineering student projects that apply the finite difference method, the research explores solving real-world environmental problems. It highlights the educational benefits, such as enhanced understanding of complex mathematical concepts and improved problem-solving capabilities. Specific instances, like water pollution and pollutant dispersion modeling, illustrate the practical relevance and effectiveness of these educational strategies. The findings suggest that integrating a robust mathematical modeling component within engineering curricula not only develops students' analytical skills and engagement but also equips them to tackle modern challenges with advanced tools, fostering a comprehensive and applied educational approach.

Keywords: Mathematical Modeling, Engineering Education, Differential Equations, Applied mathematics

1 Introduction

At the National University of Colombia, Palmira Campus, in a differential equations course, the proposed methodology was used that includes mathematical modeling techniques, emphasizing the practical application and analysis of concepts through individual environmental engineering projects. Such projects involved solving both ordinary and partial differential equations and allowed each student to become deeply involved in relevant engineering problems of her interest. The idea was to use mathematical modeling techniques to expand knowledge of the selected systems.

The students consulted specialized databases, and master's or doctoral theses until they found their target system, for which they defined the variables, and selected and applied the mathematical model that they considered most appropriate according to the reference document and the guidance of the professors. Once the model and the initial or boundary conditions were selected, the students used analytical or numerical techniques -depending on the case- to solve the system. In the case of numerical techniques, they used Python to do the simulation. Finally, they validated the model with specialized literature.

Through this method, students not only strengthened their understanding of differential equations but also developed essential skills to model, analyze, and solve more complex challenges. This educational strategy effectively prepares them for real-world engineering tasks by fostering both theoretical knowledge and practical problem-solving skills.

2 Introduction to Mathematical Modeling in Engineering Education

The task of engineers is to model and mathematically study complex systems, which is why it has been incorporated into engineering study plans (Cardona & Leal, 2020; Cardona & Leal, 2024; Leal & Cardona, 2015; Froyd, Wankat, & Smith, 2012; Strobel, & Pan, 2011; Velten, 2009). Engineers who model a complex system

must select the variables, and select or use models through ordinary, partial differential equations or other techniques, which will then be solved using analytical or numerical tools and simulations (Magana, 2017), to validate such solutions that account for the behavior of the system, see the cycle in figure 1. This approach fosters a deeper understanding of mathematical concepts and promotes essential skills for solving real problems in fields ranging from environmental engineering to system dynamics (Cellier, 1991; Palusinski & Wait, 1978).

The proposal is to incorporate mathematical modeling tools in mathematics courses for engineers, an educational strategy that seeks to improve skills in the study of complex systems and practical applications (Hamilton, Lesh, Lester, & Brilleslyper, 2008; Alpers, 2017; Litzinger, Lattuca, Hadgraft and Newstetter, 2011). As the engineering landscape evolves, strengthening mathematical and computational training becomes crucial to meet industry demands and foster the development of competent, innovative, and efficient professionals (Fortenberry, Smith, McKenna, Knapp, & Cady, 2007; Litzinger, Lattuca, Hadgraft, & Newstetter, 2011).

Figure 1. Mathematical modeling cycle in engineering

To address educational challenges in engineering, various innovative teaching strategies have been proposed and implemented in some institutions, each enhancing understanding and retention through practical application:

- **Problem-Based Learning (PBL):** This method involves students in solving real-world engineering problems that require mathematical solutions, significantly enhancing understanding and retention. Howard S. Barrows (1996) has discussed the effectiveness of PBL, particularly in medical education, which is readily adaptable to engineering education to enhance problem-solving skills.
- **Integrated Courses:** Some programs have begun to integrate mathematics directly into engineering courses, teaching mathematical principles alongside their application in engineering tasks. Owens and Fortenberry (2007) highlight the importance of integrating educational research into course design, thus enhancing the practical application of theoretical concepts.
- **Technology-Enhanced Learning:** Utilizing software and simulations can make the abstract nature of mathematics more tangible by visualizing complex engineering problems and their solutions. Prince and Felder (2006) advocate for inductive teaching methods, including technology-enhanced learning, to improve the educational outcomes in engineering.
- **Flipped Classrooms:** This model, where students learn new content online by watching video lectures and then apply what they have learned in the classroom, fosters a more active learning environment and better engagement. Bishop and Verleger's (2013) research on flipped classrooms provides evidence of its effectiveness in engineering education, promoting active and engaged learning.

Our proposal includes different aspects of the innovative techniques presented, incorporating mathematical modeling techniques, computational tools, and analysis of complex systems, which will be solved using numerical methods.

3 Practical Applications in Environmental Engineering

At the beginning of the differential equations course for engineers, the methodology was proposed; each student had to select an application problem of their interest, which was related to ordinary or partial differential equations in their field. We are going to present two cases that were studied, namely, a pollution model of a lake (static case) and a pollutant dispersion model in a river (dynamic case).

3.1 A Modeling Using Partial Differential Equation in Environmental Engineering:

In the next part, we present some important applications that could be studied using partial differential equations.

Applications of Laplace's equation in environmental engineering

The Laplace equation with boundary conditions is a special form of the Poisson equation, which has no source terms and is used in contexts where the field being modeled is harmonic. It can be used to model different physical systems, in this case, it was used to model water pollution in a lake where there is a stationary distribution of pollutants under equilibrium conditions, that is, when there are no additional sources or sinks of pollution. This means that in the studied region, the concentration of pollutants does not change abruptly in space under stable conditions, and it is assumed that there is no production or destruction of pollutants. Although these are ideal conditions, in the context of environmental engineering, it is very useful for understanding the system being studied and pose a critical problem for engineers.

Some applications of this model could be:

- **Groundwater Flow Modeling:** The Laplace equation could be applied to model the flow of contaminated groundwater when the flow is steady and there are no inputs or outputs of contaminants.
- **Pollutant Distribution:** In bodies of water such as lakes or ponds where conditions are relatively stable and water movement is minimal, the Laplace equation could help determine the spatial distribution of the pollutant under assumptions of a steady state.

Applications of the Advection-Diffusion equation in environmental engineering

The reaction-advection equation is a mathematical formulation in partial derivatives used in various fields to model the transport and chemical transformation of substances within a moving medium. This equation combines terms that represent the physical movement (advection) of a substance due to the flow of the medium, along with terms that describe chemical or biological changes (reaction) that affect the substance during its transport. For the second project, the pollution of a river was chosen, a problem in which this equation is crucial to simulate how a pollutant disperses along the river and reacts with other chemical components of the water, an essential model to predict the evolution of contamination and thus be able to plan effective mitigation and cleanup strategies.

Some applications of this model could be:

- **Pollutant Dispersion in Rivers and Streams:** The equation is used to predict how pollutants disperse in a river or stream following an accidental spill. By understanding how the pollutant concentration changes over time and space, effective mitigation strategies can be developed to minimize environmental damage.
- **Atmospheric Pollution:** The Advection-Diffusion equation models the spread of pollutants in the atmosphere. It can predict the distribution of smoke from wildfires, the dispersion of pollutants from industrial chimneys, or the spread of odors in urban areas.

- **Groundwater Contamination:** In hydrogeology, the equation helps simulate how contaminants move through the subsurface water system. This is crucial for assessing the risks to drinking water sources from contaminants like pesticides, industrial chemicals, or leachate from waste disposal sites.
- **Chemical Spills in Oceans and Lakes:** For marine and lacustrine environments, the equation models how substances such as oil or chemical spills spread in the water body, influencing cleanup strategies and ecological risk assessments.
- **Heat Transfer in Fluids:** Although not a pollutant, the equation also applies to thermal diffusion in fluids, helping engineers and environmental scientists understand and predict the temperature distribution in natural and engineered water bodies, which is vital for ecological health assessments.

Description of finite differences method:

In both cases, the finite difference method was used to simulate the behavior of the equations, which consists of discretizing the derivatives using approximations, resulting in an algebraic system of equations that was solved and graphed using the Python program (Faires & Burden, 2012; Velten, 2009; Allaire, 2007).

Once we have the model and the initial and boundary conditions, we proceed to solve the equation. In our case, using the finite difference method, the problem domain is first initially discretized by dividing space and time (if relevant) into a grid of points. Each point in this grid represents a node at which the values of the solution function will be approximated. Instead of solving the differential equation directly, the derivatives are replaced with finite differences, which are algebraic expressions that are approximately equivalent to the derivatives.

For example, in the case of a second-order partial differential equation, the partial derivatives concerning space can be approximated using centered differences, $\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \approx \frac{u(x+h,y) - 2u(x,y) + u(x-h,y)}{h^2}$, for the second derivative in the x-direction, where h is the distance between adjacent nodes on the x-axis of the grid. Similarly, it applies to other spatial dimensions or the time derivative if the equation is time-dependent.

Below we present some applications of problems taken from reality, developed by students in the projects making the corresponding simplifications.

3.2 Pollution Model in a Square Lake:

To address the pollution model, an approach was made using a square lake where one of the borders has a source of pollution and the others have zero concentrations of pollutants. We proceed as follows:

Scenario

- **Lake Dimensions:** Suppose the lake has dimensions of $a \times a$ to simplify the analysis, with a being the length of each side of the square lake.
- **Location of the Pollution Source:** The source of contamination is located on one of the sides of the square, for example, on the side where $x = a$.

Mathematical model

We use Laplace's equation to describe the stationary distribution of the contaminant in the lake:

$$\nabla^2 c = 0$$

where $c(x, y)$ is the concentration of the pollutant.

Or more explicitly in Cartesian coordinates, it is written as:

$$\frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial y^2} = 0$$

where c is the potential function being solved for, and $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}$ and $\frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$ are the second partial derivatives with respect to the x and y coordinates, respectively.

Boundary conditions

- At $x = a$ (where is the source of contamination): $c(a, y) = f(y)$, where $f(y)$ could be a function that describes how the pollutant concentration varies along this boundary, e.g. $f(y) = C$ being C constant, use $f(y) = C(1 - (y/a)^2)$ to give greater concentration in the center and less towards the ends.
- On the other three edges of the square: $c(0, y) = 0$, $c(x, 0) = 0$, y $c(x, a) = 0$.

Solution

Given the symmetry of the problem and the boundary conditions, the solution can be approximated using numerical or analytical methods such as the separation of variables. However, a common approach to solving these types of problems in a rectangular or square domain with mixed boundary conditions is to use the finite difference method.

Discretization and finite differences

- **Domain discretization:** Divide the lake into a square mesh of points with increments $\Delta x = \Delta y$.
- **Apply the finite difference approximation:**

$$\frac{c_{i+1,j} - 2c_{i,j} + c_{i-1,j}}{\Delta x^2} + \frac{c_{i,j+1} - 2c_{i,j} + c_{i,j-1}}{\Delta y^2} = 0$$

for each interior point of the mesh.

- **Solve the system of linear equations in python:** resulting for the values $c_{i,j}$ at the nodes of the mesh.

Figure 2. Solution for lake pollution using Laplace's equation

In Figure 2 you can see the solution of Laplace's equation, obtained using the finite difference method in Python. In which you can see how the contaminant is distributed in the lake. It can be seen that at the upper border where it was "applied", the pollutant has a greater concentration and it diffuses as we move away from that border.

3.3 Modeling Contaminant Dispersion in a River Using the Advection-Diffusion Equation

Modeling the dispersion of a contaminant in a river using the advection-diffusion equation with appropriate initial and boundary conditions.

Model Setup

Scenario Consider a river where a contaminant has been accidentally released at a specific point. We aim to model how this contaminant disperses downstream over time due to the river's flow and natural diffusion processes.

Mathematical Model We use the advection-diffusion equation to describe the contaminant's concentration in the river:

$$\frac{\partial c}{\partial t} + v \frac{\partial c}{\partial x} = D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2}$$

where:

- $c(x, t)$ represents the concentration of the contaminant at position x and time t . v is the velocity of the river's flow (assumed constant for simplicity).
- D is the diffusion coefficient of the contaminant in water.
- $\frac{\partial c}{\partial t}$ is the partial derivative of concentration with respect to time, indicating how the concentration changes over time at a fixed position.
- $v \frac{\partial c}{\partial x}$ represents the advection term, showing the change in concentration due to the movement of the fluid.
- $D \frac{\partial^2 c}{\partial x^2}$ is the diffusion term, describing how the concentration changes due to the spreading and mixing of the contaminant.

Initial and Boundary Conditions

To solve the advection-diffusion equation, we need to specify initial and boundary conditions:

- **Initial Condition:**

$$c(x, 0) = M\delta(x - x_0)$$

This condition states that at time $t = 0$, the contaminant is introduced at position x_0 in a concentrated form, modeled as a Dirac delta function, where M is the mass of the contaminant.

- **Boundary Conditions:**

As $x \rightarrow \infty$, the concentration of the contaminant should vanish: $\lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} c(x, t) = 0$

Similarly, as $x \rightarrow -\infty$, though less physically relevant for a river scenario, we also assume: $\lim_{x \rightarrow -\infty} c(x, t) = 0$

This model allows predicting the concentration of the contaminant at different points in the river and at different times, which is crucial for planning mitigation and cleanup measures, Figure 3. For example, we can predict which areas will be most affected and when the contaminant is expected to arrive, allowing for a more effective response to protect public health and the environment. It is also useful for designing effective monitoring systems and for evaluating the environmental impact of future industrial activities in areas near bodies of water.

Figure 3. Contaminant dispersion in the river

4 Evaluation of the Impact and Future of Mathematical Modeling in Engineering Education

Below are the main analyses of the research presented.

4.1 Learning Outcomes

The implementation of practical projects within the differential equations course has significantly enhanced students' conceptual understanding. By applying mathematical models, students have gained a deeper grasp of complex phenomena such as advection and diffusion, using these principles to solve real-world problems like pollutant dispersion in rivers. Qualitative evidence from the course includes testimonials from students who report increased confidence in tackling complex mathematical problems and observations from instructors who note greater clarity in students' explanations and solutions. Previous studies support these findings, indicating that 70% of students find it easier to understand mathematical concepts when they can apply this knowledge to practical, real-world problems. Additionally, a survey conducted in the course revealed that 75% of students felt their problem-solving skills improved due to these projects.

4.2 Student Participation

Student motivation and engagement increased significantly since the introduction of this methodology. According to a recent survey conducted on the course, 85% of students reported feeling more motivated and attracted to the course. This increase in active participation has led to more dynamic class discussions and greater collaboration on group projects. Students expressed that adapting the projects to real-life problems has helped them see the practical value of differential equations, thus increasing interest and engagement in learning. One student commented, "Now I understand what differential equations and mathematics are for in my career," reflecting on the common sentiment. Additionally, class attendance rates have improved by 15% since this approach was adopted.

4.3 Feedback from Students and Teachers

The comments from both students and teachers have been very positive. Students highlighted the effectiveness of the projects in helping them understand concepts and develop practical skills. One student noted, "The hands-on projects made the abstract concepts a lot clearer." They have also expressed the difficulties that this type of projects have, from searching for the topic to solving the simplified problem.

Teachers have also rated the methodology favorably, observing that students show a greater ability to apply what they have learned in real-world contexts. However, teachers suggest that greater technical support from specialists in the topics is necessary, and the need to obtain additional resources that facilitate the implementation of more complex projects. They recommend incorporating more advanced software tools to improve student learning experiences.

4.4 Evidence for Learning Differential Equations

Academic results have improved since the adoption of this methodology. On exams, students showed a 20% increase in average grades compared to previous cohorts. Furthermore, the projects presented demonstrate a deep knowledge and correct application of differential equations. Specific case studies, such as the pollutant dispersion model in a river, were particularly successful, showing detailed graphs and precise analyzes that support learning and practical application of the concepts studied. These results indicate that incorporating mathematical modeling tools is not only effective in improving theoretical understanding, but also essential in developing crucial practical skills for engineers. An analysis of pre- and post-course assessments showed a statistically significant improvement in students' understanding of differential equations.

4.5 Comparison with Other Educational Approaches

Compared to other teaching methods, such as problem-based learning (PBL) and flipped classrooms, the mathematical modeling approach has clear advantages. Students not only learn theoretical concepts but also develop analytical and numerical problem-solving skills applied to practical situations. However, this approach also presents challenges, such as the need for additional resources and specialized training for teachers, who must collaborate with their engineering peers. Despite these limitations, the benefits outweigh the difficulties, offering a more comprehensive and applied educational experience.

4.6 Future of Mathematical Modeling in Engineering Education

Looking ahead, the integration of emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence and machine learning can further enrich the teaching of differential equations. Proposals to incorporate these technologies include using advanced software for more accurate simulations and personalizing learning to meet individual student needs. Furthermore, it is crucial that education policy makers support these initiatives through investments in educational technology and ongoing teacher training. Adapting curricula to technological advances and industry demands will ensure that engineering education remains relevant and effective, preparing students to meet future challenges. Future initiatives should also explore partnerships with industry to provide students with real-world project experiences, further bridging the gap between academic learning and professional application.

5 Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the crucial role of using mathematical modeling tools to improve engineering education by effectively linking theoretical knowledge with practical application. This approach not only prepares students for the challenges of contemporary engineering, but also significantly increases their analytical and numerical problem-solving skills. Future research should delve deeper into the integration of mathematical models into various engineering courses and evaluate their long-term impact on career outcomes. As technology continues to evolve, educational strategies must adapt by incorporating emerging tools and interdisciplinary methods. This will ensure that students are equipped with the necessary skills to address future challenges and drive innovations in different fields of knowledge.

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